

Deracemization of binaphthyl by Suzuki diarylation: the role of electronic and steric effects

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General methods

All chemicals, including ligands **L1**, **L2**, **L4** and **L5**) were purchased from Fluorochem, while **L3** was purchased from Sigma Aldrich, if not stated otherwise and used without further purification. Solvents were purified by distillation under argon atmosphere and reactions were performed under argon atmosphere using Schlenk technique.

Methods and Characterization

Products were purified by flash chromatography by using Isolera Biotage FSKO-1107-0010 on Merck Silica Gel (60H). Merck Silica Gel F254 plates were used for thin layer chromatography and visualization was performed with UV-light (254 nm). Melting points were measured on a Büchi melting point apparatus M-565. Specific optical rotations were measured on a Jasco P-2000 polarimeter at 589 nm. NMR were recorded by VARIAN VNMRS at R.T. in CDCl₃. Chemical shifts are reported in ppm downfield to internal standard TMS (0.00 ppm), at frequency ¹H (600 MHz), ¹³C (151 MHz) and ¹⁹F (564 MHz) Coupling constants are given in Hz. HRMS spectra (70 eV, 150 μA, EI) were recorded on Voyager GC/MS Finnigan instrument with an ion source HESI (heated electrospray), the mass analyzer orbitrap (Orbitrap Velos Pro Thermo Scientific). HPLC analysis were done on a Chiralcel Daicel OD-H column with hexane and propan-2-ol as the eluents at 254nm.

Starting material

Preparation of (RS)-2,2'-diiodo-1,1'-binaphthyl (**2**, DIBN)

A mixture of 2-naphthol (50.00 g, 0.35 mol), hydrazine monohydrate (8.60 g, 10 mL, 5.82 mol) and water (2 mL) was heated in autoclave at 180°C for 72 h. Pressure reached 28 bar during the reaction. Reaction mixture was dissolved in Et₂O (2 L). 20 % solution of HCl in MeOH (100 mL) was slowly added, until white precipitate was observed. The white precipitate was filtered through fritted glass and it was dried on a vacuum pump. The obtained mixture of DABN and β-naphthylamine was stored in the form of hydrochloride salt under Ar atmosphere in freezer. A mixture of hydrochloride salts of 2,2'-diamino-1,1'-binaphthyl and β-naphthylamine (5.00 g) was dissolved in H₂O-CH₃COOH-H₂SO₄ mixture (120/20/20 mL) at room temperature. The solution was cooled to -5 °C and NaNO₂ (4.00 g, 58 mmol) was added to it in three portions. The mixture was stirred 2 h at 0°C and then carefully added to the mixture of KI (18.45 g, 0.11 mol) with slush ice (200 mL) (intensive foaming was observed). The reaction mixture was stirred overnight at room temperature. Then it was added (100mL) of CHCl₃ and (200 mL) of water. Na₂SO₃ was added to promote separation of organic and water layer. Water layer was extracted with 2x 100 mL of CHCl₃. Combined organic layers were evaporated. Purification by column chromatography on silica gel (eluent hexanes-PhMe, 5:1) gave (RS)-**2** as a yellow crystalline solid (1.80 g, 36 %).

Melting point of (RS)-**2**: 225.2-227.1 °C. ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 8.05 (d, *J* = 8.7 Hz, 2H), 7.93 (d, *J* = 8.2 Hz, 2H), 7.71 (d, *J* = 8.7 Hz, 2H), 7.51 (t, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 2H), 7.29 (t, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 2H), 7.08 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 2H). **HPLC** analysis (OD-H, 1% DME in hexane, 0.5 mL/min, 254 nm) indicated 0% *ee*: *t*_S = 17.55 min, *t*_R = 19.36 min.^{S1}

^{S1} Krascenicová, K.; Walla, P.; Kasák, P.; Uray, G.; Kappe, C. O.; Putala, M. *Chem. Commun.* **2004**, 2606-2607.

Figure S1. ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of (RS)-2.

Figure S2. HPLC chromatogram of (RS)-2.

General experimental procedure

A mixture of 2,2'-diiodo-1,1'-binaphthyl (**2**; 51 mg, 0.1 mmol), arylboronic acid (0.4 mmol), cesium fluoride (122 mg, 0.8 mmol), palladium trifluoroacetate (1.66 mg, 5 mol-%), ligand (20 mol-%) in THF (2 mL) was heated in an oil bath to 55 °C (bath temperature, real temperature of the reaction mixture 53 °C) for 24 h under an argon atmosphere. The reaction mixture was filtered through a short silica pad (eluted DCM), and the solvent was evaporated. Reaction mixture was separated by flash

chromatography on silica gel (if not stated otherwise). The final product was subjected to HPLC to determine the *ee*.

Characterization of compounds

(*R*)-2,2'-Di-*p*-tolyl-1,1'-binaphthyl (**4a**)

The reaction mixture was separated by flash chromatography (SiO₂, eluent hexanes/ethyl acetate 10/1). Then crude compound **4a** was purified by flash chromatography (SiO₂, hexanes) to provide light yellow solid in 63% yield (27.4 mg). **Melting point** of (*RS*)-**4a**: 184.0 – 186.4 °C. **¹H NMR** (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 7.92 (d, *J* = 8.2 Hz, 2H), 7.88 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 7.47 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 2H), 7.40 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 2H), 7.36 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 7.31 (t, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 2H), 6.70 (d, *J* = 7.9 Hz, 4H), 6.36 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 4H), 2.19 (s, 6H) ppm. **[α]_D²⁰** = +20.4 (*c* = 1, CHCl₃). **HPLC** analysis (OD-H, 1% propan-2-ol in hexane, 0.5 mL/min, 254 nm) indicated 98% *ee*: *t_S* (minor) = 8.5 min, *t_R* (major) = 11.6. Spectral data agreed with literature values.^{S1}

Figure S3. ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) spectrum of **4a**.

Figure S4. HPLC chromatogram of (RS)-4a.

Figure S5. HPLC chromatogram of (R)-4a.

(R)-2,2'-Bis(4-methoxyphenyl)-1,1'-binaphthalene (**4b**)

The compound **4b** was purified by flash chromatography (SiO₂, eluent hexanes/ethyl acetate 15/1) to provide light yellow solid in 82% yield (38.26 mg). **Melting point** of (RS)-**4b** 262.5 – 264.8 °C. **¹H NMR** (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 7.93 (d, *J* = 8.2 Hz, 2H), 7.88 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 2H), 7.49 – 7.45 (m, 2H), 7.39 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 2H), 7.35 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 7.33 – 7.29 (m, 2H), 6.44 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 4H), 6.39 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 3.68 (s, 6H) ppm. [α]_D²⁰ = +62.7 (*c* = 1, CHCl₃). **HPLC** analysis (OD-H, 5% propan-2-ol in hexane, 0.5 mL/min, 254 nm) indicated 94% *ee*: *t*_S(minor) = 10.7 min, *t*_R(major) = 11.1 min. Spectral data agreed with literature values.^{S1}

Figure S6. ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of **4b**.

Figure S7. HPLC chromatogram of (*RS*)-**4b**.

Figure S8. HPLC chromatogram of (R)-4b.

(R)-2,2'-Bis(4-ethylphenyl)-1,1'-binaphthalene (4c)

Figure S9. ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of 4c.

Figure S10. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of **4c**.

Figure S11. HPLC chromatogram of (*RS*)-**4c**.

Figure S12. HPLC chromatogram of (R)-4c.

(R)-2,2'-Diphenyl-1,1'-binaphthalene (4d)

The reaction mixture was separated by flash chromatography (SiO₂, eluent hexanes/ethyl acetate 10:1). Then crude product **4d** was purified by flash chromatography (SiO₂, hexanes) to provide light yellow solid in 30% yield (12.2 mg). **Melting point (RS)-4d** 229-230.2 °C. **¹H NMR** (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 7.94 (d, *J* = 8.2 Hz, 2H), 7.89 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 7.49 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 2H), 7.42 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 2H), 7.36 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 7.35 – 7.31 (m, 2H), 7.01 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 2H), 6.88 (t, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 4H), 6.43 (d, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 4H) ppm. $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{20} = +55.4$ (*c* = 0.125, CHCl₃). **HPLC** analysis (OD-H, 1% propan-2-ol in hexane, 0,5 mL/min, 254 nm) indicated 50% *ee*: *t*_s(minor) = 8.3 min, *t*_R(major) = 12.1 min. Spectral data agreed with literature values.^{S1}

Figure S13. ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of **4d**.

Figure S14. HPLC chromatogram of *(RS)*-**4d**.

Figure S15. HPLC chromatogram of (*R*)-4d.

(*R*)-2,2'-Bis[4-(methylsulfonyl)phenyl]-1,1'-binaphthalene (4e)

Figure S16. ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) spectrum of 4e.

Figure S17. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of **4e**.

Figure S18. HPLC chromatogram of *(RS)*-**4e**.

Figure S19. HPLC chromatogram of (R)-4e.

(R)-2,2'-Di(1,1'-biphenyl-4-yl)-1,1'-binaphthalene (4f)

Figure S20. ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) spectrum of 4f.

Figure S21. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of **4f**.

Figure S22. HPLC chromatogram of *(RS)*-**4f**.

Figure S23. HPLC chromatogram of (R)-4f.

(R)-2,2'-Bis(4-vinylphenyl)-1,1'-binaphthalene (4g)

Figure S24. ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) spectrum of 4g.

Figure S25. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of **4g**.

Figure S26. HPLC chromatogram of (*RS*)-**4g**.

Figure S27. HPLC chromatogram of (*R*)-4g.

(*R*)-2,2'-Bis(4-isopropylphenyl)-1,1'-binaphthalene (4h)

Figure S28. ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) spectrum of 4h.

Figure S29. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of **4h**.

Figure S30. HPLC chromatogram of *(RS)*-**4h**.

Figure S31. HPLC chromatogram of (R)-4h.

(R)-2,2'-Bis(4-*tert*-butylphenyl)-1,1'-binaphthalene (4i)

Figure S32. ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) spectrum of 4i.

Figure S33. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of **4i**.

Figure S34. HPLC chromatogram of *(RS)*-**4i**.

Figure S35. HPLC chromatogram of (R)-4i.

(R)-2,2'-Bis(4-isopropoxyphenyl)-1,1'-binaphthalene (4j)

Figure S36. ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) spectrum of 4j.

Figure S37. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of **4j**.

Figure S38. HPLC chromatogram of (*RS*)-**4j**.

Figure S39. HPLC chromatogram of (R)-4j.

(R)-2,2'-Bis(4-*tert*-butoxyphenyl)-1,1'-binaphthalene (4k)

Figure S40. ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) spectrum of 4k.

Figure S41. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of **4k**.

Figure S42. HPLC chromatogram of *(RS)*-**4k**.

Figure S43. HPLC chromatogram of (R)-4k.

(R)-2,2'-Bis[4-(diphenylamino)phenyl]-1,1'-binaphthalene (4l)

Figure S44. ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) spectrum of 4l.

Figure S45. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of **4I**.

Figure S46. HPLC chromatogram of (*RS*)-**4I**.

Figure S47. HPLC chromatogram of (R)-4l.

(R)-2,2'-Bis(3-fluoro-4-methoxyphenyl)-1,1'-binaphthalene (4m)

Figure S48. ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) spectrum of 4m.

Figure S49. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of **4m**.

Figure S50. ^{19}F NMR (565 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of **4m**.

Figure S51. HPLC chromatogram of (RS)-4m.

Figure S52. HPLC chromatogram of (R)-4m.

(R)-2,2'-Bis(3-chloro-4-methoxyphenyl)-1,1'-binaphthalene (4n)

Figure S53. ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of **4n**.

Figure S54 $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of **4n**.

Figure S55. HPLC chromatogram of (RS)-4n.

Figure S56. HPLC chromatogram of (R)-4n.

(R)-2,2'-Bis(4-methoxy-3-methylphenyl)-1,1'-binaphthalene (4o)

Figure S57. ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of **4o**.

Figure S58. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of **4o**.

Figure S59. HPLC chromatogram of (RS)-4o.

Figure S60. HPLC chromatogram of (R)-4o.

(R)-2,2'-Bis[4-methoxy-3-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl]-1,1'-binaphthalene (4p)

Figure S61. ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of **4p**.

Figure S62. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of **4p**.

Figure S63. ^{19}F NMR (565 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of **4p**.

Figure S64. HPLC chromatogram of *(RS)*-**4p**.

Figure S65. HPLC chromatograph of (R)-4p.

(R)-5,5'-(1,1'-Binaphthalene-2,2'-diyl)bis(2-methoxybenzaldehyde) (4q)

Figure S66. ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) spectrum of 4q.

Figure S67. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of **4q**.

Figure S68. HPLC chromatogram of *(RS)*-**4q**.

Figure S69. HPLC chromatogram of (R)-4q.

(R)-2,2'-Bis(3,4,5-trimethoxyphenyl)-1,1'-binaphthalene (4r)

Figure S70. ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of **4r**.

Figure S71. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of **4r**.

Figure S72. HPLC chromatogram of (RS)-4r.

Figure S73. HPLC chromatogram of (R)-4r.

(R)-2,2'-Bis(3-methoxyphenyl)-1,1'-binaphthalene (4s)

The compound **4s** was purified by column chromatography (SiO₂, hexanes/DCM 4/1) to provide light yellow solid in 45% yield (21 mg).

Melting point of (RS)-**4s**: 128.3 – 130.9 °C. **¹H NMR** (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 7.94 (d, *J* = 8.3 Hz, 2H), 7.90 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 7.50 – 7.46 (m, 4H), 7.40 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 7.35 (t, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 2H), 6.83 (t, *J* = 7.9 Hz, 2H), 6.57 (d, *J* = 8.2 Hz, 2H), 6.10 (d, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 2H), 6.00 (s, 2H), 3.13 (s,

6H) ppm. [α]_D²⁰ = +91.5 (*c* = 0.75, CHCl₃). **HPLC** analysis (OD-H, 5% propan-2-ol in hexane, 0,5 mL/min,

254 nm) indicated 27% *ee*: $t_S(\text{minor}) = 9.4 \text{ min}$, $t_R(\text{major}) = 10.4 \text{ min}$. Spectral data agreed with literature values.^{S1}

Figure S74. ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) spectrum of 4s.

Figure S75. HPLC chromatogram of (RS)-4s.

Figure S76. HPLC chromatogram of (R)-4s.

(R)-2,2'-Bis(3,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-1,1'-binaphthalene (4t)

Figure S77. ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) spectrum of 4t.

Figure S78. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of **4t**.

Figure S79. HPLC chromatogram of *(RS)*-**4t**.

Figure S80. HPLC chromatogram of (R)-4t.

(R)-5,5'-(1,1'-Binaphthalene-2,2'-diyl)bis(2-fluorobenzaldehyde) (4u)

Figure S81. ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) spectrum of 4u.

Figure S82. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of **4u**.

Figure S83. ^{19}F NMR (565 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of **4u**.

Figure S84. HPLC chromatogram of (RS)-4u.

Figure S85. HPLC chromatogram of (R)-4u.

(R)-2,2':1',1'':2'',2'''-Quaternaphthalene (4v)

Figure S86. ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of **4v**.

Figure S87. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of **4v**.

Figure S89. HPLC chromatogram of (RS)-4v.

Figure S90. HPLC chromatogram of (R)-4v.

SDE of (*R*)-2,2'-Bis(4-ethylphenyl)-1,1'-binaphthalene (**4c**)

Table S1. *ee* of the diarylated derivative **4c** determined in the fractions from the flash chromatographic separation (Conditions: silica gel: Merck Silica Gel (60H), eluent hexanes, flow rate 25 mL/min, fraction volume 10 mL).

Fraction	Isolated product [mg]	<i>ee</i> [%]
1	1.2	68*
2	2.4	90
3	4.9	85
4	3.7	85
5	2.2	82
6	1.2	50
7	0.9	50*

* Difficult integration due to impurities

XYZ coordinates of calculated structures

C	-1.46113000	1.19974900	-0.07348500
C	-0.06920000	1.20323800	-0.07706300
C	0.66530700	0.01564100	-0.00722000
C	-0.05416200	-1.18633700	0.06259400
C	-1.44236200	-1.19502400	0.07016900
C	-2.16807900	-0.00052000	0.00260500
H	-2.00700200	2.13801700	-0.13248000
H	0.44076800	2.16352300	-0.15081200
H	0.49453900	-2.12283000	0.11150100
H	-1.97884800	-2.13951500	0.12808300
B	2.23216100	-0.00879500	-0.00429100
O	2.86342400	-1.21078600	-0.13827300
H	3.82348300	-1.09709100	-0.10123100
O	3.01215400	1.11059600	0.13226200
H	2.49833800	1.91381300	0.27793800
C	-3.67515300	-0.02194900	0.00749900
H	-4.05789800	-0.51362100	0.90772600
H	-4.08788900	0.98936800	-0.02713600
H	-4.06224800	-0.57495900	-0.85463800

C	0.92311200	1.42962200	0.00007100
C	-0.45453300	1.29975100	0.00000600
C	-1.08275100	0.04422800	-0.00004900
C	-0.25442400	-1.08201100	0.00000200
C	1.13469900	-0.98141000	0.00006800
C	1.72710900	0.28348300	0.00008500
H	1.40906300	2.39952500	0.00009600
H	-1.04737500	2.21391900	-0.00001900
H	-0.71287200	-2.06702200	-0.00001700
H	1.73857200	-1.88127200	0.00012600
B	-2.63631000	-0.13286700	-0.00015400
O	-3.14504500	-1.40023700	0.00011800
H	-4.11210500	-1.37721500	0.00016200
O	-3.52997100	0.90788700	-0.00009700
H	-3.10756800	1.77474300	-0.00013200
O	3.06568400	0.50415700	0.00018400
C	3.91362700	-0.62345100	-0.00020900
H	3.75755100	-1.23899100	-0.89414300
H	4.93206800	-0.23568000	-0.00028400
H	3.75783500	-1.23940200	0.89349700

C	1.95631700	1.19334300	-0.00003300
C	0.56490500	1.20484900	-0.00002100
C	-0.17561300	0.01680400	0.00001100
C	0.52916000	-1.19461700	0.00003200
C	1.92015400	-1.21832000	0.00001600
C	2.63547500	-0.02259900	-0.00001500
H	2.51005200	2.12724800	-0.00005300
H	0.05963000	2.17031600	-0.00003400
H	-0.03151000	-2.12507900	0.00006000
H	2.44847300	-2.16698200	0.00003300
H	3.72138200	-0.03752000	-0.00002800
B	-1.74497700	-0.00128200	0.00004000
O	-2.37561300	-1.21065400	0.00002100
H	-3.33607100	-1.09463800	-0.00067800
O	-2.52585300	1.12465600	0.00002900
H	-2.01772600	1.94429000	0.00016000

C	-0.77982800	0.98840800	0.00036000
C	0.60657500	1.11634700	0.00026300
C	1.45656600	0.00783600	0.00001200
C	0.85517000	-1.26046600	-0.00011100
C	-0.52212500	-1.41065100	-0.00009800
C	-1.35601000	-0.28345500	0.00013300
H	-1.39640600	1.88013100	0.00066400
H	1.01605900	2.12626700	0.00042800
H	1.49030100	-2.14177700	-0.00030700
H	-0.96418300	-2.40341300	-0.00027600
B	3.01812400	0.12929900	-0.00008700
O	3.75314400	-1.02017600	-0.00015400
H	4.69966200	-0.82022600	-0.00013800
O	3.69774700	1.31992300	-0.00003300
H	3.12017600	2.09207200	0.00001500
S	-3.09899900	-0.58927200	0.00029500
C	-3.79329500	1.08030900	-0.00064700
H	-3.50165600	1.63277700	-0.89649800
H	-4.87732400	0.95457600	-0.00124900
H	-3.50271200	1.63349900	0.89509200

C	0.23230100	1.18390200	0.25520700
C	1.62167100	1.18227200	0.25437500
C	2.35403700	0.01771400	-0.00392900
C	1.63309200	-1.15419900	-0.26884400
C	0.24419300	-1.16349800	-0.26756300
C	-0.47888600	0.00660300	-0.00397600
H	-0.31080000	2.09697300	0.48226800
H	2.13442200	2.12213700	0.45666800
H	2.17958800	-2.06745100	-0.48685100
H	-0.29258500	-2.07929500	-0.49930000
B	3.92192700	-0.01181000	-0.00462900
O	4.54759400	-1.13277200	-0.46479500
H	5.50825000	-1.03978700	-0.39723400
O	4.70430900	1.02280600	0.43783600
H	4.19451600	1.75760500	0.79912700
C	-1.96231600	0.00006800	-0.00130300
C	-2.68410200	1.07897000	-0.52503700
C	-2.67103700	-1.08586400	0.52574500
C	-4.07488300	1.07264100	-0.52195200
H	-2.14762000	1.91665000	-0.96181600

C	-4.06180000	-1.09274700	0.52971900
H	-2.12409500	-1.91891900	0.95826700
C	-4.76886700	-0.01334400	0.00580800
H	-4.61797800	1.91442700	-0.94058600
H	-4.59461000	-1.94006600	0.95036900
H	-5.85437000	-0.01859400	0.00841500

C	-1.17821900	-1.01829800	-0.14506900
C	0.20490700	-1.12354400	-0.12641000
C	1.02919500	0.00472000	-0.01379400
C	0.40510600	1.25495700	0.07052800
C	-0.97956100	1.36886100	0.05607200
C	-1.79554000	0.23534400	-0.04146500
H	-1.78458400	-1.91187700	-0.25885800
H	0.64389800	-2.11582600	-0.22569100
H	1.02187700	2.14598800	0.14633000
H	-1.44431300	2.34934100	0.12591900
B	2.59396400	-0.09267600	0.01210200
O	3.31631200	1.05832100	-0.10207900
H	4.26447400	0.87312400	-0.04945300
O	3.28142600	-1.27021000	0.15111900
H	2.70597800	-2.03207200	0.28835800
C	-3.25987200	0.40217400	-0.03810100
H	-3.60543700	1.42736200	-0.16407700
C	-4.16562700	-0.56340600	0.12101300
H	-3.88903500	-1.60175200	0.27865600
H	-5.22691900	-0.34064500	0.10935000

C	1.00739300	1.22789400	-0.18419100
C	-0.37477700	1.21527800	-0.03294700
C	-1.10112800	0.01882900	-0.04749800
C	-0.38296900	-1.17273500	-0.21546600
C	0.99812900	-1.16504800	-0.37075100
C	1.71349100	0.03564200	-0.35943500
H	1.54925600	2.17096900	-0.16796800
H	-0.88496200	2.16765000	0.10975800
H	-0.92529400	-2.11412700	-0.22637700
H	1.53551300	-2.10143100	-0.50540500
B	-2.65966400	-0.02384900	0.11141800
O	-3.26164600	-1.23524300	0.28853000
H	-4.22148600	-1.13219800	0.35250000

O	-3.46076800	1.08835500	0.07686100
H	-2.97354600	1.89995200	-0.10834100
C	3.21848700	0.03883600	-0.46930300
H	3.54175900	-0.78568000	-1.11443500
H	3.55118300	0.96696900	-0.94731700
C	3.88272000	-0.09629300	0.90590400
H	3.57668800	-1.02820900	1.39091500
H	4.97318300	-0.09470500	0.81988300
H	3.58726300	0.73074600	1.55869900

C	0.57052300	1.38968500	-0.00225600
C	-0.81737800	1.28611500	-0.00213800
C	-1.45773700	0.04320100	-0.00016100
C	-0.64582800	-1.10036000	0.00154800
C	0.73936300	-1.00241200	0.00150000
C	1.37110600	0.24669700	-0.00035800
H	1.04158400	2.36977600	-0.00388400
H	-1.39820600	2.20831400	-0.00388800
H	-1.11996800	-2.07792600	0.00294700
H	1.34048300	-1.90894100	0.00290600
B	-3.01788300	-0.10913600	0.00024500
O	-3.54478400	-1.36777500	-0.00163300
H	-4.51155300	-1.33210200	-0.00106900
O	-3.89223700	0.94662400	0.00197400
H	-3.45400500	1.80571000	0.00381300
C	2.88366200	0.35532300	-0.00050000
H	3.13525400	1.42366300	-0.00213800
C	3.48680300	-0.27037700	1.26222900
H	3.27755500	-1.34489000	1.30116900
H	4.57378000	-0.14029900	1.27507000
H	3.07213200	0.18543000	2.16582900
C	3.48691300	-0.27436600	-1.26110500
H	3.07273600	0.17880100	-2.16626000
H	4.57395900	-0.14475600	-1.27407400
H	3.27726500	-1.34892400	-1.29692400

C	0.37278200	1.23064000	0.00036300
C	-1.02045100	1.21988400	0.00036900
C	-1.74843100	0.02839000	0.00000700
C	-1.01552400	-1.16710400	-0.00035400
C	0.37180400	-1.16226800	-0.00037800

C	1.09866900	0.03735300	-0.00000600
H	0.88813400	2.18486300	0.00066300
H	-1.53350200	2.18155700	0.00072800
H	-1.55291300	-2.11138000	-0.00062300
H	0.90159700	-2.11150200	-0.00067600
B	-3.31527100	-0.01428700	0.00000900
O	-3.92875300	-1.23304400	0.00072100
H	-4.89067600	-1.12996200	0.00057600
O	-4.11331800	1.10023100	-0.00064400
H	-3.61518600	1.92606700	-0.00138500
C	2.62859100	-0.00357200	-0.00000800
C	3.11691000	-0.74667300	1.25504800
H	2.74333200	-1.77449100	1.28630100
H	4.21193900	-0.78549600	1.26779900
H	2.77956700	-0.23695200	2.16333500
C	3.11696100	-0.74625500	-1.25527400
H	2.77959700	-0.23629200	-2.16342200
H	4.21199300	-0.78500300	-1.26803800
H	2.74346200	-1.77409200	-1.28685100
C	3.24573600	1.39850500	0.00023900
H	2.95284700	1.96803100	-0.88811200
H	2.95297100	1.96766300	0.88886400
H	4.33747600	1.31753100	0.00014400

C	-0.05544600	1.50411400	0.22645500
C	1.31558100	1.31523400	0.23304000
C	1.89345200	0.06116800	-0.01794600
C	1.01983300	-1.00001500	-0.27430200
C	-0.36291000	-0.83804500	-0.28903300
C	-0.90844100	0.42529900	-0.03927300
H	-0.50148800	2.47361100	0.42154900
H	1.94389100	2.17810300	0.45222800
H	1.43697300	-1.98473400	-0.46648000
H	-0.99735900	-1.69305100	-0.49081900
B	3.43748600	-0.18075400	-0.01911400
O	3.89581600	-1.46244600	-0.13062700
H	4.86304900	-1.47665100	-0.13682700
O	4.37109900	0.81989400	0.08005900
H	3.98086900	1.70129800	0.11015900
O	-2.23221700	0.72153100	-0.04386400
C	-3.19213900	-0.31824600	-0.23533100
H	-2.86454200	-0.95685400	-1.06638200
C	-3.35007200	-1.13800300	1.03945600
H	-4.07536100	-1.94283500	0.88747900
H	-2.40228500	-1.58101600	1.35567100
H	-3.71081900	-0.49112400	1.84490300

C	-4.48152500	0.38303400	-0.62650200
H	-4.79641400	1.05602500	0.17648500
H	-4.33680700	0.97117500	-1.53568200
H	-5.27471500	-0.34924900	-0.80064700

C	-0.23339100	1.55594300	-0.00036700
C	-1.60280400	1.36148000	-0.00037500
C	-2.16892200	0.07755800	-0.00006100
C	-1.28074200	-1.00145600	0.00024100
C	0.10182000	-0.83344500	0.00027700
C	0.64031900	0.45794000	-0.00002100
H	0.20198200	2.54963200	-0.00063700
H	-2.23817400	2.24684000	-0.00073200
H	-1.68533700	-2.00992700	0.00045800
H	0.73437600	-1.70947800	0.00052600
B	-3.71025300	-0.17910600	-0.00001000
O	-4.15526000	-1.47060300	-0.00062500
H	-5.12226700	-1.49486900	-0.00039100
O	-4.65586000	0.81529500	0.00068100
H	-4.27608700	1.70169000	0.00140500
O	1.95176900	0.80286800	0.00001200
C	3.05508400	-0.12171600	0.00002600
C	4.26295500	0.81476300	-0.00004300
H	5.19273100	0.23901700	-0.00015700
H	4.24192100	1.45352800	-0.88720500
H	4.24210600	1.45348000	0.88716100
C	3.07587200	-0.96356900	1.27729300
H	3.01637000	-0.30595000	2.14938000
H	2.25734700	-1.68217200	1.33545600
H	4.01639900	-1.52069400	1.32876000
C	3.07569500	-0.96365200	-1.27718500
H	2.25661500	-1.68159000	-1.33558700
H	3.01696500	-0.30601300	-2.14930800
H	4.01580300	-1.52151300	-1.32834000

C	0.00680200	-1.25330700	-0.38361300
C	1.37533600	-1.22534900	-0.14185900
C	2.09184300	-0.02282700	-0.10375700
C	1.38013000	1.16441400	-0.32492500
C	0.01294100	1.15480200	-0.57322900
C	-0.68085900	-0.05689200	-0.59320800

H	-0.54295900	-2.18814000	-0.42500000
H	1.88285200	-2.17392900	0.03051500
H	1.91739800	2.10842200	-0.30516000
H	-0.53277700	2.07302100	-0.76605900
B	3.63499900	0.03037400	0.16029700
O	4.21019400	1.24307200	0.40483300
H	5.16541900	1.14881200	0.52605500
O	4.44857800	-1.07331000	0.15460200
H	3.98620900	-1.88355100	-0.09047600
O	-2.01681100	-0.08119900	-0.89720900
C	-2.97573900	0.01859200	0.18349700
C	-4.31792100	-0.04923800	-0.53349000
H	-5.13984600	0.01641900	0.18533300
H	-4.40409000	0.77565300	-1.24608700
H	-4.40234300	-0.99102800	-1.08272100
C	-2.81994600	-1.15372100	1.14952400
H	-2.90670200	-2.10312400	0.61179500
H	-1.85137600	-1.12505500	1.65756200
H	-3.60489700	-1.11439300	1.91106400
C	-2.82300500	1.34850300	0.91805300
H	-1.85593200	1.41524800	1.42520900
H	-2.90913400	2.18266900	0.21479600
H	-3.61000300	1.44873600	1.67191700

C	1.19445600	-0.99827200	0.69393600
C	2.58215100	-0.99648000	0.68504100
C	3.32123700	-0.01392300	0.01471000
C	2.59664000	0.97951400	-0.65920200
C	1.20965200	0.98823100	-0.67816900
C	0.48950800	-0.00330800	0.00320800
H	0.64589200	-1.76235600	1.23527700
H	3.08988900	-1.78055300	1.24614400
H	3.14149800	1.75437200	-1.19127600
H	0.67045600	1.75914900	-1.21955300
B	4.88509800	0.00736100	-0.00462400
O	5.51337800	1.09466100	-0.53975900
H	6.47360100	0.98033000	-0.51178300
O	5.67069300	-1.00731400	0.48032200
H	5.16162700	-1.76278400	0.79696800
N	-0.92096400	0.00075200	-0.00314700
C	-1.63887300	-1.22145900	-0.01946500
C	-1.21533300	-2.28041100	-0.83018700
C	-2.78394700	-1.37836000	0.76880800
C	-1.92080600	-3.47810400	-0.83890000
H	-0.33117200	-2.15515200	-1.44755900
C	-3.49364600	-2.57346200	0.73854100

H	-3.11116100	-0.55674500	1.39841200
C	-3.06527800	-3.63154900	-0.05963700
H	-1.57980600	-4.29153000	-1.47209700
H	-4.38125600	-2.68049100	1.35459100
H	-3.61794600	-4.56518300	-0.07525400
C	-1.63298900	1.22676700	0.01436800
C	-1.20439700	2.28365100	0.82488000
C	-2.77775400	1.38830900	-0.77333800
C	-1.90496600	3.48425600	0.83394400
H	-0.31935300	2.15602600	1.44043700
C	-3.48264200	2.58617000	-0.74240300
H	-3.10826700	0.56849400	-1.40357800
C	-3.04941100	3.64233400	0.05570900
H	-1.55920900	4.29663100	1.46583300
H	-4.36991900	2.69703300	-1.35824500
H	-3.59779800	4.57848100	0.07127300

C	0.85984900	1.10430700	0.00002200
C	-0.51634100	1.10248800	-0.00006500
C	-1.23210600	-0.10618100	-0.00008400
C	-0.49488200	-1.29154300	0.00001400
C	0.90027600	-1.29433800	0.00010800
C	1.59880300	-0.08804900	0.00009200
H	-1.00553000	2.07408100	-0.00013400
H	-1.02621500	-2.23834600	0.00001800
H	1.43708400	-2.23590900	0.00021900
B	-2.79683700	-0.16128600	-0.00022200
O	-3.39727100	-1.38655000	0.00008700
H	-4.36022700	-1.29400300	0.00020100
O	-3.60549400	0.94499100	-0.00001700
H	-3.12175900	1.77918200	0.00003900
O	2.94288900	0.05194500	0.00018700
C	3.71138100	-1.13248900	-0.00020500
H	3.51175700	-1.73436500	-0.89462300
H	4.75327200	-0.81428200	-0.00025500
H	3.51196200	-1.73481200	0.89396600
F	1.53344100	2.26184700	0.00003600

C	1.00045300	-0.73082400	0.00061100
C	-0.36670100	-0.94880100	0.00028300
C	-1.27633200	0.11073100	0.00004200

C	-0.74467500	1.40883200	0.00013800
C	0.62263300	1.62923000	0.00031900
C	1.53187300	0.56419800	0.00053400
H	-0.68087100	-1.99056800	0.00032400
H	-1.42461200	2.25515000	-0.00001800
H	1.03836000	2.63153700	0.00029300
B	-2.82707000	-0.10462300	-0.00031500
O	-3.62761700	0.99973700	-0.00011600
H	-4.56099600	0.74545900	-0.00029000
O	-3.43401000	-1.33344300	-0.00061600
H	-2.81429900	-2.07217500	-0.00071100
O	2.83940000	0.90745800	0.00064600
C	3.84984700	-0.09006600	-0.00170400
H	3.78832500	-0.71741000	-0.89444200
H	4.79119600	0.45924100	-0.00246300
H	3.79081900	-0.71924900	0.88990900
F	1.80918400	-1.81318700	0.00092400

C	0.99720900	0.74080800	-0.06692600
C	-0.36798900	0.95539100	-0.00244400
C	-1.26971600	-0.11255100	-0.01033500
C	-0.73484600	-1.40667700	-0.08146800
C	0.63412600	-1.62155700	-0.13441000
C	1.53245200	-0.55025700	-0.12298700
H	-0.69043000	1.99298800	0.05427100
H	-1.41214400	-2.25513700	-0.08581900
H	1.05373600	-2.62105300	-0.18191800
B	-2.82063000	0.09643200	0.05133900
O	-3.61135300	-1.00185200	0.21857700
H	-4.54631200	-0.75317000	0.22106600
O	-3.43390600	1.31723800	-0.05776900
H	-2.82160600	2.04220300	-0.22969900
O	2.84966500	-0.85315100	-0.20045800
C	3.80366000	0.04701300	0.34801000
H	3.47424500	0.42127900	1.32236000
H	4.71699500	-0.53584800	0.47032100
H	3.98984400	0.88989300	-0.32029500
F	1.81491200	1.81397600	-0.08515800

C	0.84795100	0.60688800	-0.10457000
C	-0.51204700	0.85821900	0.02316900

C	-1.44590200	-0.18114400	-0.03435900
C	-0.97011000	-1.48525300	-0.22345500
C	0.38845300	-1.74096400	-0.35652000
C	1.31153200	-0.69768400	-0.30138000
H	-0.82045200	1.88891500	0.18425500
H	-1.68252200	-2.30352000	-0.26621400
H	0.76782600	-2.74554400	-0.51644700
B	-2.98797000	0.07906600	0.10044400
O	-3.80283800	-0.99540000	0.29561400
H	-4.72978200	-0.72090500	0.33745800
O	-3.56151500	1.32000700	0.02679600
H	-2.93733700	2.02348000	-0.18747500
O	2.64063800	-0.95488100	-0.46620300
C	3.34006000	-1.13037800	0.76023900
H	2.93858500	-1.98768500	1.31342400
H	4.38135900	-1.31691500	0.49710700
H	3.27412100	-0.23150100	1.38280700
Cl	1.98695000	1.92131900	-0.03973700

C	0.80154500	0.78109800	0.00002200
C	-0.57507800	0.92110700	-0.00002600
C	-1.42346800	-0.19393200	-0.00002600
C	-0.82485900	-1.45660900	0.00004200
C	0.55737100	-1.61438600	0.00009500
C	1.39197900	-0.49372200	0.00007400
H	-0.96846100	1.93546900	-0.00007600
H	-1.45970900	-2.33762400	0.00005400
H	0.98466700	-2.61019400	0.00017300
B	-2.98484900	-0.06979000	-0.00010400
O	-3.71728400	-1.22085200	0.00004600
H	-4.66427900	-1.02298300	0.00006200
O	-3.66463100	1.11941800	-0.00005900
H	-3.09343500	1.89630300	-0.00003900
O	2.73947200	-0.53872300	0.00015100
C	3.35453900	-1.81034800	-0.00019500
H	3.08233400	-2.38176400	-0.89501700
H	4.42734800	-1.62173500	-0.00034700
H	3.08265200	-2.38210800	0.89451000
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C	-0.85592800	-1.33914600	0.02699400
C	-1.56062100	-0.13608500	0.00426500
H	1.01220900	2.03816800	-0.06079000
H	1.08489600	-2.25421300	0.03636500
H	-1.37760800	-2.28888700	0.04803800
B	2.81263100	-0.13619500	-0.00017300
O	3.44916000	-1.33876600	-0.11807800
H	4.40842600	-1.21825100	-0.08584700
O	3.59405100	0.98540200	0.11926800
H	3.08081200	1.79263200	0.24220900
O	-2.91693000	-0.04472700	0.00658700
C	-3.65472700	-1.24677900	0.03200200
H	-3.43868400	-1.82702100	0.93691600
H	-4.70540600	-0.95716700	0.02856400
H	-3.44253900	-1.86235900	-0.85016900
C	-1.67546500	2.37393000	-0.05635500
H	-2.32358300	2.45515400	0.82196700
H	-1.01123900	3.24136200	-0.08106900
H	-2.32878500	2.40947400	-0.93381800

C	-0.56893700	-0.27700400	0.09615100
C	0.75557400	-0.68328100	-0.01570400
C	1.80722700	0.23612900	0.04019000
C	1.48306900	1.58893700	0.21317300
C	0.16505500	2.01144800	0.33673800
C	-0.86573300	1.07601700	0.28304000
H	0.94616900	-1.74297200	-0.16780200
H	2.28805400	2.31688900	0.25768700
H	-0.08030300	3.05726100	0.49395700
B	3.31053500	-0.19623400	-0.08251100
O	4.24787300	0.78558400	-0.20455700
H	5.13753200	0.40810400	-0.25220500
O	3.73636100	-1.49684200	-0.07022100
H	3.03065700	-2.13816400	0.07476000
O	-2.17075100	1.44302900	0.44109600
C	-2.71462500	2.16486500	-0.65673800
H	-2.70577600	1.54612700	-1.55992400
H	-3.74220700	2.40596900	-0.38511200
H	-2.15735600	3.09044900	-0.83953700
C	-1.70057200	-1.26170300	0.01778600
F	-2.39626800	-1.32761800	1.15709300
F	-1.25250100	-2.50121500	-0.24581400
F	-2.56719100	-0.94329000	-0.95879300

C	0.87066600	0.81155600	0.00002500
C	-0.52073000	0.87418500	0.00000400
C	-1.32030100	-0.26853900	0.00001300
C	-0.65956000	-1.50577500	0.00004300
C	0.72676200	-1.60921300	0.00007000
C	1.50266500	-0.44568500	0.00005900
H	-0.94495000	1.87744900	-0.00003300
H	-1.25603500	-2.41403700	0.00005000
H	1.19188300	-2.58757900	0.00010900
B	-2.88585100	-0.21361400	-0.00000800
O	-3.56757800	-1.39576000	-0.00017600
H	-4.52238600	-1.23952700	-0.00015400
O	-3.61137200	0.94661200	0.00012900
H	-3.06911500	1.74465400	0.00029400
O	2.85556500	-0.43871700	0.00010300
C	3.52701100	-1.68298200	-0.00009000
H	3.27931800	-2.26471300	-0.89492100
H	4.59084000	-1.44863200	-0.00018800
H	3.27952500	-2.26488000	0.89469100
C	1.65114400	2.07149900	-0.00000400
H	2.74949200	1.96520100	0.00009000
O	1.13147700	3.16659700	-0.00013400

C	-0.62089300	-1.23544700	-0.11946500
C	0.77121600	-1.21574900	-0.01479300
C	1.46101800	0.00141200	0.01342400
C	0.75043500	1.20301300	-0.05817800
C	-0.64034700	1.18980000	-0.17294400
C	-1.32655400	-0.03052400	-0.22431700
H	1.31349700	-2.15162300	0.08293600
H	1.29996300	2.13640500	-0.01832500
B	3.02372300	0.04519300	0.11848300
O	3.62389400	1.21268500	0.48952300
H	4.58678100	1.11785700	0.48046800
O	3.82687500	-1.03233900	-0.15472100
H	3.33207100	-1.78185200	-0.50740000
O	-1.38867600	-2.35556500	-0.12451600
O	-1.42717100	2.29396100	-0.24046600
C	-0.77807200	3.54663800	-0.21209100
H	-1.56651600	4.29558800	-0.28453500

H	-0.22262500	3.68796300	0.72272400
H	-0.09031000	3.65677900	-1.05870200
C	-0.72173500	-3.59411000	-0.04887700
H	-1.49837100	-4.35801200	-0.08168000
H	-0.04004200	-3.73280900	-0.89721200
H	-0.15650100	-3.68960100	0.88666900
O	-2.68053600	-0.05120800	-0.38657600
C	-3.38855000	0.08489300	0.83689600
H	-3.14954900	1.03934100	1.31878000
H	-4.44981400	0.05791800	0.58576200
H	-3.15140100	-0.74375100	1.51422700

C	-0.67617600	-1.23097200	0.07559800
C	0.70971200	-1.37269900	0.11636200
C	1.54286800	-0.25680900	0.04129600
C	0.96718800	1.01611800	-0.08951500
C	-0.41612500	1.16859400	-0.13225300
C	-1.24528800	0.03512800	-0.05584400
H	1.09696500	-2.38549700	0.20459100
H	1.62402100	1.87622400	-0.15426700
B	3.10417700	-0.38494800	0.10119600
O	3.85833300	0.71022200	-0.20597500
H	4.80050600	0.51177700	-0.11089300
O	3.75757300	-1.53566200	0.45461400
H	3.15735900	-2.24340000	0.71902500
O	-1.47342400	-2.33576900	0.20510000
O	-1.07054400	2.35421000	-0.23240700
C	-0.27696400	3.51730000	-0.33300100
H	-0.97392100	4.35088600	-0.41710100
H	0.34944100	3.65089000	0.55700100
H	0.36392600	3.48410600	-1.22168000
C	-2.17982200	-2.68280100	-0.98058800
H	-2.75423500	-3.57932600	-0.74304900
H	-2.85414400	-1.87815100	-1.28481200
H	-1.47690800	-2.90470400	-1.79258300
O	-2.60399400	0.17014400	-0.12095900
C	-3.18494000	0.52316400	1.12867000
H	-2.79761900	1.48702100	1.47461700
H	-4.25985800	0.59982200	0.95975300
H	-2.98268600	-0.25220200	1.87607500

C	-0.61610700	-1.27522400	-0.21141700
C	0.77275200	-1.39179200	-0.10638800
C	1.58816100	-0.27009500	-0.00246600
C	0.99536800	1.00164200	-0.00456400
C	-0.38215000	1.13500600	-0.12992600
C	-1.20414100	-0.00699900	-0.23262800
H	1.16940200	-2.40422100	-0.08363900
H	1.63430400	1.87294800	0.07965700
B	3.14605800	-0.39086600	0.11619800
O	3.85969100	0.71711800	0.47134100
H	4.80706100	0.52087700	0.48330000
O	3.83605800	-1.54887500	-0.12677900
H	3.26905400	-2.26361000	-0.44141500
O	-1.31435300	-2.43566500	-0.34465200
O	-1.03934000	2.32454500	-0.19493700
C	-0.25389700	3.49714200	-0.16286300
H	-0.95212300	4.32924200	-0.25209100
H	0.29914600	3.58148100	0.77991400
H	0.45427900	3.52083900	-0.99903600
C	-2.55321200	-2.56910100	0.33408400
H	-2.71444700	-3.64221900	0.45339500
H	-2.50584500	-2.10205200	1.32526500
H	-3.37387500	-2.13045100	-0.23598900
O	-2.55035200	0.11314500	-0.43932600
C	-3.29078700	0.68619100	0.63167700
H	-3.04517100	1.74181800	0.76139100
H	-4.34298500	0.57994500	0.36242700
H	-3.09864000	0.14696700	1.56759300

C	0.45387100	-1.17321300	-0.08659000
C	-0.93551500	-1.19356300	-0.07291200
C	-1.67024000	-0.00204800	-0.06055900
C	-0.97365300	1.21085500	-0.04026400
C	0.41719000	1.24574200	-0.05604400
C	1.14060000	0.04817600	-0.08003400
H	-1.44107100	-2.15429400	-0.08124200
H	-1.48492500	2.17097300	-0.00988400
B	-3.23769800	-0.05451600	-0.06653300
O	-3.84957900	-1.24186400	0.20563800
H	-4.81095500	-1.15306400	0.14218700
O	-4.02781500	1.03126400	-0.33854400
H	-3.52105800	1.81131500	-0.59499700
O	1.15454000	-2.34923900	-0.15960600
O	1.06380000	2.45040100	-0.10251200
C	1.80099900	2.76163200	1.07379600
H	2.24179500	3.74547000	0.90719200

H	1.13379700	2.80362000	1.94312400
H	2.59065200	2.02607800	1.24861100
C	1.86937600	-2.66815700	1.02909800
H	2.36170700	-3.62372500	0.84371700
H	2.61681200	-1.90228700	1.25571300
H	1.17786600	-2.77176700	1.87333200
O	2.50997200	0.08129200	-0.09919300
C	3.05013900	-0.18272400	-1.39195300
H	4.13498000	-0.13801100	-1.28764000
H	2.74895100	-1.17652400	-1.73719800
H	2.71601000	0.57977100	-2.10374400

C	-0.57202700	2.03739800	-0.10121600
C	0.72751500	1.55303500	-0.08900300
C	0.97431900	0.17241100	-0.02460100
C	-0.11346300	-0.69632200	0.02289300
C	-1.42532700	-0.21223900	0.01606800
C	-1.65822800	1.16255100	-0.04534300
H	-0.75711800	3.10593900	-0.15725400
H	1.55151900	2.26148300	-0.15227600
H	0.04015000	-1.77041300	0.06523700
H	-2.66636200	1.56031700	-0.05369100
B	2.43087300	-0.41308900	0.00125600
O	2.60252000	-1.74732400	-0.21706600
H	3.53735400	-1.98721900	-0.14885800
O	3.54444600	0.34884000	0.24170000
H	3.33252000	1.26547700	0.45541100
O	-2.40453700	-1.15371800	0.07101300
C	-3.74043900	-0.70553700	0.06134000
H	-3.97004700	-0.15187000	-0.85747300
H	-4.36094100	-1.60029700	0.10851400
H	-3.95497600	-0.06814000	0.92811400

C	-0.38981800	2.31868300	-0.06822600
C	0.82798200	1.63786900	-0.06251000
C	0.86194100	0.24315400	-0.02126600
C	-0.34858600	-0.46591500	0.01026000
C	-1.56497800	0.21368900	0.00824500
C	-1.58169600	1.61330500	-0.02978400
H	-0.41032100	3.40363900	-0.10504000
H	1.74964600	2.21511200	-0.11080700
H	-0.31052600	-1.54942500	0.03370500
H	-2.54318600	2.11628700	-0.03198000

B	2.21166500	-0.55722800	-0.00662900
O	2.16989200	-1.90591200	-0.20861900
H	3.05803900	-2.28598300	-0.15478100
O	3.43477800	0.02134000	0.20773200
H	3.37527700	0.96351900	0.40661200
O	-2.78395400	-0.38680800	0.04077400
C	-2.81060000	-1.79690200	0.07022100
H	-2.31206600	-2.18665600	0.96582900
H	-3.86319300	-2.07903900	0.08882800
H	-2.33319100	-2.22357100	-0.81995600

C	-1.28552600	-1.07655900	0.01891800
C	-1.19627200	0.31852300	0.02972900
C	0.05964600	0.93558100	0.01335000
C	1.22106100	0.15925900	-0.01170800
C	1.12194300	-1.23530300	-0.02929100
C	-0.12817800	-1.84929800	-0.01609100
H	-2.09879200	0.91977200	0.08392200
H	2.18249200	0.65909700	-0.01387500
H	-0.20100400	-2.93082700	-0.02657600
B	0.19012700	2.49948200	0.00975600
O	1.38650500	3.05851900	0.34914100
H	1.34569300	4.02235300	0.27398600
O	-0.83981800	3.33775200	-0.33087200
H	-1.61448500	2.85956400	-0.65069900
O	-2.45336000	-1.77345200	0.04207700
O	2.18642100	-2.07875600	-0.05941100
C	3.47319500	-1.50022100	-0.05936700
H	4.17749400	-2.33181000	-0.07906000
H	3.62761800	-0.87023300	-0.94342100
H	3.64095000	-0.90017200	0.84273400
C	-3.65252600	-1.03527100	0.08351400
H	-4.45925100	-1.76803200	0.09555400
H	-3.71086500	-0.41608300	0.98710700
H	-3.75853000	-0.39380500	-0.80025500

C	0.64934400	1.32160200	-0.02717000
C	-0.69385000	0.96383700	-0.03440600
C	-1.05371900	-0.39697500	-0.01414600
C	-0.06447900	-1.36973500	0.01203200
C	1.28879300	-1.00208900	0.02804400
C	1.64870300	0.33936700	0.01013000
H	-1.46159100	1.72934100	-0.09133400

H	-0.31899200	-2.42439000	0.01927900
H	2.67951400	0.67125800	0.01773600
B	-2.56258200	-0.83019600	-0.00159100
O	-2.88725000	-2.10034900	-0.37115200
H	-3.83926700	-2.24915600	-0.28298100
O	-3.57583500	0.01331600	0.37668100
H	-3.24607800	0.85399100	0.71682000
O	1.11079400	2.60131300	-0.05625500
O	2.18052800	-2.02514200	0.06106900
C	3.55088600	-1.69409300	0.07024100
H	4.09122900	-2.64022400	0.09516000
H	3.83213200	-1.13654000	-0.83142400
H	3.81181700	-1.10122000	0.95538200
C	0.15450300	3.63509800	-0.10082100
H	0.71678700	4.56862900	-0.11768000
H	-0.46551700	3.56687700	-1.00303100
H	-0.49409500	3.61724700	0.78384500

C	0.80947300	-1.19995300	-0.02988500
C	-0.58387100	-1.20905200	-0.03736300
C	-1.30040500	-0.01018100	-0.01309800
C	-0.60531300	1.19927000	0.01591400
C	0.78889000	1.20756600	0.02888300
C	1.51034900	0.00914400	0.00715300
H	-1.07257500	-2.17901800	-0.08832400
H	-1.13439000	2.14619200	0.02730900
H	2.59157100	0.01702500	0.01557200
B	-2.87131000	-0.00184100	-0.00793600
O	-3.52077600	1.15986200	-0.29991600
H	-4.47877200	1.04027900	-0.23559200
O	-3.62458500	-1.10763400	0.28655400
H	-3.08697300	-1.86354900	0.55297400
O	1.41380000	-2.41871200	-0.06148500
O	1.37696800	2.43302200	0.06360800
C	2.78409100	2.49111700	0.07034100
H	3.04347200	3.54944100	0.09518600
H	3.20185900	1.99480000	0.95524300
H	3.20862900	2.03496900	-0.83270600
C	2.82210900	-2.45575500	-0.06726700
H	3.09741000	-3.50986200	-0.09962500
H	3.23235100	-1.94636800	-0.94800000
H	3.23877900	-1.99994500	0.83948800

C	1.33600700	0.32360000	0.00000900
C	-0.00043900	0.73141100	-0.00000600
C	-1.05158200	-0.18275300	0.00000600
C	-0.72653900	-1.55133600	0.00002700
C	0.59049300	-1.99246000	0.00004100
C	1.60166100	-1.04288700	0.00003100
H	-0.16619600	1.80761700	-0.00004900
H	-1.53388100	-2.27789400	0.00003100
H	0.85015400	-3.04508500	0.00006100
B	-2.55923300	0.25823800	-0.00001000
O	-3.50464300	-0.72336000	-0.00020200
H	-4.39528800	-0.34511200	-0.00016100
O	-2.97679800	1.55965400	0.00018700
H	-2.25984100	2.20511500	0.00039800
C	2.42658200	1.32770100	-0.00004000
H	3.45600000	0.92797900	-0.00004300
O	2.21869000	2.51981700	-0.00010900
F	2.87668100	-1.45470600	0.00004400

C	-3.66990400	0.11831500	0.01315300
C	-2.73418300	1.11974400	-0.02427200
C	-1.34775700	0.81491000	-0.02473800
C	-0.94073100	-0.54784000	0.01397600
C	-1.93382400	-1.56282400	0.05207800
C	-3.26573700	-1.23932200	0.05171300
H	-0.66241400	2.86601900	-0.10284900
H	-4.72790200	0.36173800	0.01324600
H	-3.04024900	2.16226500	-0.05433300
C	-0.35067100	1.82532700	-0.06556000
C	0.44495900	-0.85096700	0.01311800
H	-1.61485100	-2.60140800	0.08112600
H	-4.01774300	-2.02158000	0.08076200
C	1.40823000	0.13510000	-0.01957500
C	0.97751300	1.49201000	-0.06144600
H	0.75169000	-1.89441900	0.03929800
H	1.71296300	2.29411000	-0.10766300
B	2.92516200	-0.26250900	-0.00066600
O	3.94462300	0.63606200	0.17792000
H	3.63583900	1.53536400	0.33984100
O	3.25489100	-1.57609400	-0.16160600
H	4.21336300	-1.69601000	-0.10729300

